

Kinetics of thermal dehydration and decomposition of hydrated chlorides of 3d transition metals (Mn-Cu series). Part-II. Dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

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An attempt has been made to study the thermal dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air as well as in flowing nitrogen atmosphere using the simultaneous DTA/TG method. In static air or self-generated atmosphere, the salt dehydrates in three steps losing about 2.0, 1.1 and 1.0 moles of H_2O , respectively which do not undergo any significant change with increase in heating rate from 2° to 10°/min. In flowing nitrogen atmosphere dehydration also takes place in three steps. While the average loss of 2.1 moles of H_2O in the first step does not show any variation with heating rate, loss in the second step tends to increase with corresponding decrease in the third step with increase in heating rate. Consequently, the total loss of H_2O in nitrogen atmosphere is about 0.5 moles higher than in the static air. While in static air nucleation and growth appears to be the most appropriate mechanistic model, in flowing nitrogen only the first step obeys this model. The other two steps obey the contracting phase boundary model. A comparison of the thermal dehydration characteristics between MnCl_2 and FeCl_2 hydrates has been presented.

In the previous communication¹ the kinetics of thermal dehydration of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been studied using the isoconversion method of Ozawa-Flynn-Wall (OFW)², the essential features of which have also been presented in the same communication. The method has some distinct advantages over many other methods mainly because it is non-discriminatory i.e. independent of any mechanistic model. The other advantage is that the method is capable of determining Arrhenius parameters (AP) of a complex process disguised in an apparently single thermoanalytical curve (TG/DTA/DSC). The occurrence of such a process can be detected from the conversion dependence of activation energy which otherwise is difficult to know *a priori*. The far-reaching importance of determining AP by the isoconversion method and its predictive capability of thermal stability of compounds beyond the experimental range of temperature have been discussed in detail by Vyazovkin and Lesnikovich³.

The thermal dehydration behavior of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ should be close to that of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. However, no work worth its name has been carried out on the dehydration of this two salts, especially hydrated FeCl_2 . This is mainly because it is extremely difficult to prepare pure $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which has a strong tendency to be oxidized in the presence of air. Because of the low thermal stability of FeCl_3 in the presence of moisture it may decompose before the dehydration

is completed⁴. Consequently, the kinetics of such a complex process can only be resolved by the isoconversion method. In this paper an attempt has been made to elucidate the kinetics of dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ under static air as well as under flowing N_2 atmosphere.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the simultaneous DTA and TG curves of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at two typical heating rates under static air and flowing N_2 atmosphere. The shaded or hatched areas under the DTA peaks at 10°/min have been used for the estimation the heats dehydration. Both DTA and TG traces in Fig. 1 show that the dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air or self-generated atmosphere takes place in three steps losing about 2, 1 and 1 moles H_2O . In flowing nitrogen condition the pattern of dehydration is basically similar to that in static air. The resulting thermoanalytical data are given in Table 1. Unlike MnCl_2 hydrate the initial melting at temperature below 40° is not clearly resolved as distinct endothermic peak, but appear as shoulder in static air. It may be noted from Table 1 that DTA peak temperature for the first step of dehydration in air increases from 63.5° at 2°/min to 76° at 10°/min. For the 2nd and the 3rd steps of dehydration the DTA peak temperatures show similar increase of about 13–15° with increase in heating rate and the reaction is complete within 200°. Therefore the second and the third steps of dehydration are of special interest to us as these water

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Fig. 1. Simultaneous TG/DTA traces at two typical heating rates for the dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air and in flowing nitrogen atmosphere. The hatched areas under the DTA peaks at 10° have been used to estimate heats of dehydration.

molecules are directly coordinated to the metal ion.

The initial melting of the hydrated salt appears as a distinct endo peak at 39° under the flowing N_2 atmosphere (see Fig. 1). Similarly, another weakly resolved peak at around 110° in the second step of dehydration in air appears as a distinct endo peak in N_2 atmosphere. In fact, this endothermic peak is even larger than the other peak at 120° in 2nd step of dehydration. Further, the temperatures of both the peaks increase with increase in heating rate, suggesting that none of them is due to any phase change. The interesting aspect is that even a subtle break is not observed in the TG curve for the corresponding DTA peak at temperature around 110° . The possibility of sublimation of either FeCl_3 or FeCl_2 is also ruled out at such low temperature. It is there-

fore difficult to make definite assignment to this two peaks.

At the heating rate of $2^\circ/\text{min}$ while the moles of H_2O lost in the second step in N_2 atmosphere is 1.09, in the third step it is significantly high at 1.36 mole. On increasing the heating rate the moles of H_2O lost in the 2nd step increase, but decrease considerably in the 3rd step. Further, at $2^\circ/\text{min}$ one of the peaks (118°) belonging to the 2nd step is shifted to the 3rd step. All these suggest that the 1st endo peak in the 2nd step of dehydration in N_2 is possibly due to the decomposition of either FeCl_2 or FeCl_3 in the presence of residual moisture. This reaction is aided by flowing N_2 which prevents the gaseous products from being built-up over the crucible. As a result, the DTA peak is resolved more clearly. In general, the overall mass loss in flowing nitrogen environment is more than that observed in static air, although the DTA peak temperatures for the three steps of dehydration do not show much variation under the two different conditions (Table 1).

Heats of dehydration :

The heats of the three steps of dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air have been estimated from the area covered by the DTA traces at $10^\circ/\text{min}$. The detail procedure has been described in the previous communication¹. The ΔH_{reac} values are 123, 77.6 and 87 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively and are closely similar to those found for the dehydration of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The higher value for the 1st step is due to the loss of two moles of water from $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ compared to one mole from MnCl_2 hydrate.

Kinetics of dehydration :

The complex nature of the dehydration of FeCl_2 hydrate, especially in flowing nitrogen atmosphere suggests that it is essential to carry out the simultaneous DTA/TG experiment at different heating rates to enable us to use OFW method for kinetic analysis. Like $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the first step of dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air is also accompanied with melting which results in an appreciable temperature fluctuation. Therefore, no attempt has been made to study the kinetics of this step of dehydration.

Fig. 2 shows the plot of α vs T for the second step of dehydration in air and Fig. 3 depicts the corresponding isoconversion plot at different values of α . It may be noted that good linear relationship comprising the three heating rates is followed for $\alpha = 0.2-0.7$. Since the slope values of the linear portions joining the heating rates of 4° and $8^\circ/\text{min}$ for $\alpha = 0.1$ and 0.15 are very close to the plots for $\alpha = 0.2-0.7$, it was considered to include 0.1 and 0.15 in the estimation of average value of E . The same argument, however, may not be applied to include $\alpha = 0.8$ and 0.9 as the slope values of the linear portions joining 4° and $8^\circ/\text{min}$ are

Table 1. Effect of heating rate on the TG/DTA parameters of dehydration of FeCl_2 hydrate in static air and in flowing nitrogen environments

Heating rate °C/min	1st step of dehydration			2nd step of dehydration			3d step of dehydration			Total loss of H_2O (moles)
	Temp. range (Ti-Tc) °C	DTA peak temp. °C	Moles of H_2O lost	Temp. range (Ti-Tc) °C	DTA peak temp. °C	Moles of H_2O lost	Temp. range (Ti-Tc) °C	DTA peak temp. °C	Moles of H_2O lost	
(A) Dehydration in static air										
2	45-69	63.5	1.87	97-122	113.5	1.38	145-168	162	1.14	4.39
4	53-81	71.5	2.02	97-130	126	1.01	144-175	168	1.02	4.05
6	42-90	71.5	1.93	92-138	121.5	1.11	138-185	171	1.04	4.08
8	45-95	75	2.08	95-140	125	1.12	140-195	174	1.04	4.14
10	45-100	76	2.00	100-140	126	1.11	140-200	178	1.00	4.11
(B) Dehydration in nitrogen flow condition										
2	45-78.5	39, 61	2.07	83-107	100	1.09	107-162	118, 155	1.36	4.52
4	43-90	39, 66.5	2.20	90-135	104, 125	1.68	135-178	168	0.75	4.63
6	44-94	39, 70	2.08	94-140	108, 130	1.70	140-183	170	0.69	4.47
8	43-98	39, 75.5	2.10	98-150	113, 140	1.88	150-193	174	0.66	4.64

Ti = temperature of inception from DTA curve, Tc = temperature of completion from DTA curve.

Fig. 2. Plot of α vs T at different heating rates for the second step of dehydration in air.

very low and would reduce the accuracy of the overall kinetic parameters.

Table 2 shows that the E values tend to increase initially and then decrease slowly from $\alpha = 0.25$ to 0.7 giving an av. value of $147.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Such a high E value indicates that dehydration of this involves considerable structural rearrangement. The average θ values calculated according to the procedure given in the preceding communication¹ are shown in Table 3. Using the av. θ values the isothermal time (t) for at least three temperatures viz. 370, 380 and 390 K are calculated corresponding to different α values from 0.1 to 0.7. The mechanistic model that fits best to these

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log(\text{heating rate})$ vs $1/T$ at different levels of α (isoversion) for the second step of dehydration in air.

data is found to be $F1$ that is, first order growth with rapid random nucleation.

The plot of α vs T for the third step of dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air and the corresponding isoconversion plots are similar as shown in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. It may be noted that linear relationships exist for the almost entire conversion range and the E values calculated from the slopes are given in Table 2. To examine if

Table 2. Activation energy (E) values obtained by the isoconversion method for different steps of dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air and in flowing N_2 atmosphere

α	Dehydration in static air			Dehydration in flowing N_2 atmosphere			
	2nd. step	3rd. step		1st step		2nd. step	3rd. step
	E kJ mol ⁻¹	E kJ mol ⁻¹	Mean E kJ mol ⁻¹	E kJ mol ⁻¹	Mean E kJ mol ⁻¹	E kJ mol ⁻¹	E kJ mol ⁻¹
0.05	–					89.2	
0.10	154.7	95.6		203.9		86.5	
0.15	154.7						
0.20	172.9	109.2		127.4		77.4	
0.25	182.0						
0.30	171.1	104.6		100.1	143.8	68.3	
0.40	145.6	95.6		87.4		63.7	100.1
0.50	127.4	91.0		78.8		58.3	102.0
0.60	112.8	85.5		72.8		51.0	109.2
0.70	104.6	85.5	95.3	72.8		48.2	104.7
0.80		72.8		63.7		43.7	104.7
0.90		63.7		59.2		41.0	91.0
0.95				52.8			91.0
Overall mean	147.3	89.3		69.6		62.7	100.4

Table 3. Average values of reduced time (θ) calculated from three heating rates using the corresponding mean E values in Table 2

α	Dehydration in static air			Dehydration in flowing N_2 atmosphere			
	2nd step	3rd step		1st step		2nd step	3rd step
	$\alpha = 0.1-0.7$ (min $\times 10^{20}$)	$\alpha = 0.1-0.7$ (min $\times 10^{11}$)	$\alpha = 0.1-0.9$ (min $\times 10^{11}$)	$\alpha = 0.1-0.3$ (min $\times 10^{23}$)	$\alpha = 0.4-0.95$ (min $\times 10^{11}$)	$\alpha = 0.05-0.90$ (min $\times 10^9$)	$\alpha = 0.4-0.95$ (min $\times 10^{12}$)
0.05						5.568	
0.10	1.473	4.607	0.855	1.303		6.205	
0.15	2.040	–	–	–		–	
0.20	2.567	5.795	1.093	2.732		7.310	
0.25	3.170	–	–	–		–	
0.30	4.081	6.920	1.298	3.986		8.433	
0.40	5.000	7.921	1.518		4.661	9.649	2.884
0.50	6.613	9.003	1.746		5.879	11.310	3.417
0.60	8.459	10.080	1.971		7.221	13.040	4.012
0.70	11.040	11.460	2.263		9.158	14.370	4.732
0.80		13.470			11.690	17.680	5.652
0.90		17.070			16.050	21.150	6.955
0.95					20.360		7.731

the last two E values at $\alpha=0.8$ and 0.9 have any effect on the overall mechanism, two av. E values, one for $\alpha=0.1-0.7$ and the other for $\alpha = 0.1-0.9$ have been considered for the calculation of av. θ and the isothermal time t at different conversion levels in the temperature range 420–440 K. It has been observed that A1.5 is the best fit model in both the cases suggesting that mechanism does not change even

by including the last two low E values in estimating the av. E value.

Fig. 4 illustrates α vs T plots at different heating rates for the first step of dehydration in N_2 atmosphere. Fig. 5 shows good linear isoconversion plots valid for almost entire α range. Table 2 shows that up to 30% conversion the E values are quite high and therefore put into one group with

Fig. 4. Plot of α vs T at different heating rates for the first step of dehydration in flowing nitrogen atmosphere.

an average of $143.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The remaining E values comprising $\alpha = 0.4-0.95$ are put into another group with an av. value of 69 kJ mol^{-1} . Following the same procedure as described in the foregoing paragraphs it is found that for the initial stage ($\alpha = 0.1-0.3$) $A1.5$ is the most appropriate model in the temperature range $320-330 \text{ K}$, and for the later group $F1$ is found to be the best fit model. In other words, for the entire 1st step of dehydration in N_2 atmosphere nucleation and growth of the product phase is the rate-controlling mechanism.

The plot of α vs T for the 2nd step of dehydration in flowing N_2 condition at different heating rates and the corresponding isoconversion plots are similar in nature as shown in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively and yield good linear relationship for $\alpha=0.05-0.90$. However, the systematic decrease in E values with increase in α suggests complex process of dehydration which makes it difficult to identify

Fig. 5. Plot of $\log(\text{heating rate})$ vs $1/T$ at different levels of α (isoconversion) for the first step of dehydration in nitrogen atmosphere.

any cut-off E value without ambiguity. The overall mean E value of 62.7 kJ mol^{-1} is used to calculate av. θ values and from these, isothermal time t at $370, 380$ and 390 K for the entire α range. The best fit model is found to be the contracting phase boundary with spherical symmetry ($R3$).

Fig. 6 shows the plot of α vs T at three heating rates ($4^\circ-8^\circ/\text{min}$) for the third step of dehydration in N_2 atmosphere. The isoconversion plots in Fig. 7 show that in the initial

Fig. 6. Plot of α vs T at different heating rates for the third step of dehydration in flowing nitrogen atmosphere.

stage ($\alpha = 0.1-0.3$) linear relationship is not followed comprising the three heating rates. This is attributed to the difference in the nature of the initial stages of the TG curves at 4° and $6^\circ/\text{min}$ with that at $8^\circ/\text{min}$ as can be noted from Fig. 6. However, satisfactory linear behavior is followed in the α range $0.4-0.95$ for which the mean E value is found to be $100.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (see Table 2). Using the mean E value av. θ values and from which isothermal time t for different fractional conversions are calculated at $430, 440$ and 450 K .

Fig. 7. Plot of $\log(\text{heating rate})$ vs $1/T$ at different levels of α .

Table 4. Kinetic models and Arrhenius parameters derived from isothermal time at different fractional conversions for the dehydration of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Steps of dehydration	Average θ range (min)	α range	Temp. range (K)	Kinetic model (Code)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	Arrhenius parameters		
						E (kJ mol^{-1})	$\log A$ (min^{-1})	R^2
Dehydration in static air :								
2nd step	(1.473–11.040) $\times 10^{-20}$	0.1–0.7	370–390	F1	0.9982	147.3	7.69	1.0
3rd step	(0.855–2.263) $\times 10^{-11}$	0.1–0.7	420–440	A1.5	0.9997	95.3	10.0	1.0
do	(4.607–17.070) $\times 10^{-11}$	0.1–0.9	425–440	A1.5	0.9974	91.2	10.33	1.0
Dehydration in flowing nitrogen atmosphere :								
1st step	(1.303–3.986) $\times 10^{-23}$	0.1–0.3	320–330	A1.5	0.9998	143.9	22.00	1.0
do	(4.661–20.360) $\times 10^{-11}$	0.4–0.95	340–350	F1	0.9999	69.5	10.18	1.0
2nd step	(5.568–21.150) $\times 10^{-9}$	0.05–0.95	370–390	R3	0.9997	63.2	7.59	0.9989
3rd step	(2.884–7.731) $\times 10^{-12}$	0.4–0.95	430–450	R3	0.9986	100.4	11.05	1.0

Though both $R2$ and $R3$ show almost similar correlation coefficient (R^2) as best fit models, $R3$ is chosen from lower standard deviation.

Comparison of the thermal dehydration behavior of MnCl_2 and FeCl_2 hydrates :

Both Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} chlorides occur as tetrahydrate and both dehydrate in air (self-generated atmosphere) as well as in flowing N_2 atmosphere in three steps at closely similar temperatures. However, there are differences in mode and mechanism of dehydration. While MnCl_2 hydrate loses about one mole of H_2O in each step in static air, FeCl_2 loses about 2 moles of H_2O in the first step and one mole each in the subsequent steps under the same condition. Therefore, MnCl_2 does not dehydrate completely in static air due to its high affinity for water.

In flowing N_2 condition MnCl_2 hydrate loses about two moles of H_2O in the second step and one mole each in the first and third steps, thereby showing total loss of 4 moles of H_2O compared to about 3.2–3.3 moles in static air. In flowing nitrogen, FeCl_2 hydrate also exhibits higher dehydration (~ 0.5 mol) but not as higher as in the case MnCl_2 hydrate. It is also observed that in N_2 atmosphere the number of moles of H_2O lost in the 1st step of dehydration of MnCl_2 hydrate decrease with increase in heating rate, besides merging of the two endothermic peaks due to melting and dehydration into a single peak at tem-

perature close to melting. An opposite behavior is observed in the case of FeCl_2 hydrate. The endo effect due to melting which remains suppressed in the static air is clearly resolved in the first step in the N_2 atmosphere, although the number of moles of water lost is same as that in the static air.

The other notable difference is that in nitrogen atmosphere the 2nd step of dehydration of FeCl_2 hydrate exhibits two distinct endo effects, a phenomenon not observed for the dehydration of MnCl_2 hydrate. Since the mass loss in the 3rd step tends to decrease with increase in heating rate, the additional loss i.e. more than the loss of one mole of water in the 2nd step is possibly due to the decomposition of either FeCl_2 or FeCl_3 .

Regarding the heats of dehydration, there is a close similarity between the two salts. Since $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows the loss of 2 moles of H_2O in the 1st step of dehydration, ΔH value is almost double that found for MnCl_2 hydrate. The ΔH values for the 2nd and the 3rd steps of dehydration of both the salts are reasonably close. The results suggest that the structural changes that occur in the two salts during dehydration are essentially similar.

As far as the kinetics is concerned there are some notable differences. In the case of MnCl_2 hydrate while $R2$ or $R3$ appears to be the primary mechanism of dehydration in static air, in flowing N_2 atmosphere $F1$ and $A1.5$ are found to be the best fit model. In the case of FeCl_2 hydrate an opposite

trend is observed for dehydration under the two different environments.

Experimental

Material : Freshly procured Pro-Analysi grade $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany was used. About 4–5 g greenish white crystalline sample was lightly ground in AnalaR grade acetone in an agate mortar for about 2–3 min. The solvent was allowed to evaporate and the ground sample was transferred into a small (20 ml) sample bottle and securely capped. The sample bottle was preserved in a desiccator over silica gel. Even under this storage condition some oxidation takes place after 3–4 weeks as indicated by the appearance of slightly brownish color. This sample was rejected and a fresh sample was collected from the original bottle and the experiments were finished as

quickly as possible. Chemical analysis showed that the extent of such oxidation was about 5% of the total iron.

Method : Simultaneous TG/DTA of the ground sample was carried out according to the procedure described in the preceding paper¹.

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